

Growth, Poverty and Inequality Interconnections: A Review from Bangladesh

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Abstract

This paper explores the propositions that economic growth is a necessary condition to achieve poverty reduction, but that a reduction in inequality may also be a precondition for sustained growth. Economic growth increase average per capita income, thereby reducing the rate of poverty. However, the pace of poverty alleviation depends on the increase of average income of the poor due to economic growth. If income level of the poor increases more than that of average income, rate of poverty decreases rapidly. Alleviation of relative poverty depends not only on economic growth but also on redistribution of national income. Alleviation of poverty reduces inequality which in turn stimulates economic growth. This paper confirms these growth, poverty and inequality propositions in the case of Bangladesh economy.

Keywords: Economic growth, Bangladesh, poverty, inequality.

1. Introduction

Poverty and income inequality have become a global problem. Some parts of the world see reduction of poverty and income inequality whereas other parts see the opposite. Because of sluggish economic and alarming population growth the problem of poverty becomes serious in developing countries. Unequal distribution of national income also widens the gap between the rich and the poor. In some countries, the poor becomes poorer and the rich becomes even richer day by day. Both accelerated economic growth and reduction of inequality are immense necessary factors for the alleviation of poverty. Economic growth enhances earnings of the poor, thereby pushing them above the poverty line. On the other hand, reducing inequality through greater redistribution of income reduces both absolute and relative poverty. However, reduction of inequality also

promotes economic growth. This paper attempts to review links among economic growth, poverty and inequality. Light will also be shed on the cases where growth-inequality proposition holds or not. Finally, this paper will focus on Bangladesh delving into the effect of economic growth on poverty, inequality; and the vice versa.

2. Global Poverty and Inequality Scenario

Over the period percentage of poor people is decreasing globally. However, there is variation in falling in the percentage of poor people across the regions. Figure 1 illustrates headcount ratio of poor people living under \$1.90 per day in developing countries by different.

Figure 1: Poverty Headcount Ratio by Region (\$ 1.90/day at 2011 PPP)

Source: World Development Index 2015, World Bank.

regions of the world during the period of 1981-2012. During this period number of poor people falls as well as poverty headcount ratios go down across the world. However, falling in headcount ratio follows different patterns in different regions. Poverty headcount ratios fall drastically over the period in South Asia and East Asia & Pacific, while the ratios fall slowly in Middle East & North Africa and Latin America & Caribbean regions. Towards the early 2010s developing countries in Europe and Central Asia saw fall in poverty headcount ratio, albeit slight increase in the ratio in 1990s and early 2000s. In Sub-Saharan Africa, headcount ratio decrease very slowly. In 2012, poverty headcount ratio was highest (about 43 percent) in Sub-Saharan Africa, whereas it was lowest (about 2 percent) in Europe & Central Asia. In other regions the ratio varies between 5 to 15 percent (WB 2015).

Table 1. Gini index of household income inequality by region (early 1990s and late 2000s)

Region	No. of countries	Gini index early 1990s	Gini index late 2000s	Percentage change
Africa	26	48.0	44.4	-7%
Arab States	6	36.1	36.0	0%
A&P	13	35.9	40.0	13%
ECIS	19	33.0	43.8	35%
LAC	20	51.4	48.4	-5%
All	84	38.5	41.5	11%

Source: UNDP (2013)

Although poverty headcount ratio has been falling globally, global inequality has been rising over the period. Increasing inequality is one of the main set-backs in combating poverty. Table 1 shows Gini indexes for different regions in the 1990s and 2000s. Compared to 1990s Gini indexes for Africa and Latin America declined in late 2000s by 7 % and 5% , respectively. During this period no change is recorded in Arab States. However, Asia and Pacific and ECIS regions saw significant increase in Gini index. Inequality increased by 35% in ECIS. Overall Gini increased by 11 percent during the period. Comparatively, inequality is higher in Latin American countries especially in Brazil. Household income inequality increases in high-income and low-and-middle-income countries including a number of developing countries (such as China and India). Moreover, those countries experienced faster economic growth saw faster increase in income inequality (UNDP 2013:70).

Figure 2. Global Gini coefficient compared to the Ginis of selected countries.

Figure 2 illustrates Gini coefficients of selected countries with the Gini of the world. Brazil is the most unequal country where Gini coefficient fluctuates around 0.6. Sweden is the most equal country where Gini coefficient started falling from 0.3 in middle of the 60s and continued until 1980 then it rose slightly until 2000. A rising trend of Gini is recorded in USA. Rising to 0.4 in towards the beginning of 1900s, since then it has been plateaued. Global inequality remains all the same with Gini coefficient of 0.7 throughout 1900s and 2000s.

3. Growth, Poverty and Inequality Propositions

There is no denying that alleviation or eradication of poverty requires sustain and accelerated economic growth. Steady growth will generate employment opportunities for the unemployed poor, on the other hand, growth will increase income level of the existing employed poor that will improve the poor's relative position in the society. However, relative poverty reduction requires not only growth but also fair distribution of national income as well. Remittance inflows earned abroad by the migrant workers, professionals and charity inflows have significant contribution to poverty alleviation in some poor countries like Bangladesh. Therefore, the synergy of growth, reduction of inequality and remittance inflows play important role in reducing poverty. Kraay (2005) showed, with cross-country data, that growth in average incomes account for 70 % variance in headcount measure of poverty in short run and 93% in long run. Whereas, changes in relative incomes account for remaining 30% of that variance in the short run, and 3% in long run. Thus, economic growth play vital role in reducing poverty across the globe. Similarly, Dollar and Kraay (2002) found positive association between economic growth and increase in income of the poor. They studied the systematic relationship of growth and average income of the poorest quintile with the data of 92 countries spanning four decades. They didn't find any systematic relationship between overall average income and average income of the poorest quintile. These two variables vary equiproportionately. The share of income of the poorest quintile does not vary systematically with the average income as well. This relationship holds across the regions and in different economic conditions-- normal and recession times. However, they didn't find any systematic relationship between the average incomes of the poorest quintile and some pro-growth macroeconomic policies such as low inflation, moderate size of the government, sound financial development, respect for the rule of law, and trade openness. These policies raise the average income as well as average incomes of the poor with same proportion. Democratic institutions and public spending on social services, however, systematically affects incomes of the poor. Arguably, only economic growth may not be enough for reducing relative poverty and inequality. Some literatures find that even with increasing inequality the poor benefits from the growth. Ravallion (2004a) explains that with given existing inequality the income gains by the rich from distribution-neutral growth is higher than that of the poor, although the poor gain in absolute terms. Thus, poverty is reduced with increase in growth and vice-versa. The author estimated „growth elasticity“ of poverty equal to 2.50 meaning 1 percent increase in mean income reduces the proportion of people living under the poverty line (1\$/day measure) by on an average 2.5 percent. Even the author found the growth elasticity of poverty is as high as 4.3 (Ravallion 2004b).

Investment in public health and education has profound effect on poverty and inequality reduction. But Dollar and Kraay finds that public expenditure on education doesn't have any systematic relation in increasing incomes of the poor. Criticizing this finding Gundlach et al.(2004) showed

that higher stock of human capital increases not only incomes of the poor but also affects income distribution thereby, affecting income inequality. Pro-poor growth policy may reduce both absolute and relative poverty. With the view of greater redistribution government may pursue expansionary public expenditure targeting the poor. Larger public expenditure in health and education, rural infrastructure development, social safety net programs, employment generation for the poor will reduce absolute poverty at same time reduce inequality. However, imposition of higher tax to finance distributional expenditure may distort other productive sectors in the economy. If major share of tax revenue comes from indirect taxes then it pushes inflation up. Especially in developing country, poor are vulnerable to rise in price of basic food items as a major share of their incomes is spent on buying food items. In consequence, redistribution fund is expected to be collected from less distortionary sources as well as price hike of basic consumer items that the poor people consumes must be checked.

Turning to inequality-growth propositions, there are debates among existing literatures whether inequality is good or bad for growth. Barro (2000) discussed four different strands of inequality-growth relationship. Firstly, as rich people saves relatively more than the poor does an unequal distribution of income towards the rich will pave the way of physical capital accumulation thereby, increasing growth. Secondly, at low level of investment in human capital the marginal product of human capital is higher than the marginal product of physical capital. Consequently, the gain of redistribution of income from rich to poor through investment in human capital will outweigh the loss associated with fall in physical capital. As a result, growth effect will be higher than that of the pre-intervention time. Thirdly, existence of income inequality is viewed as bad for economic growth. To decrease inequality government opt for higher taxation to achieve income redistribution. To avoid high tax payment the tax payers spend much time and effort, legally and illegally, which leads to loss of efficiency and income. Initial level of inequality both in income and wealth is inversely related with subsequent growth (Alesina and Rodrick 1994). Fourthly, inequality has a negative impact on the socio-political stability of a country. Extreme inequality may lead to revolt by the poor demanding confiscation of private property or nationalization of private assets. Inequality results in coups, crime, rioting that lead to inefficiency. Households incur extra cost to protect their property from anarchy. In this turmoil condition investment also goes down putting downward pressure on economic growth. Socio-political instability reduces investment by many ways--by imposing excessive tax on capital to ensure more redistribution, social unrest distorts in production process there by reducing productivity of capital and labour, and in troubled period uncertainty looms large that helps capital flight (Alesina and Peroti 1996).

According to Kuznets inverse U shape curve, first inequality rises and reaches at peak then falls as income goes up (see Kuznets 1955). With some exception this finding is an empirical regularity (Barro 2000). At low level of GDP inequality stimulate the growth reducing absolute poverty. If income has gone up sufficiently, more equalizing redistribution can enhance the growth process. At that stage removing wealth inequality especially land reforms spur the economic growth further. Land distribution is doubly effective in reducing inequality and promoting growth. The success stories are the East Asian tiger economies especially the South Korea.

Barro(2000) found little overall association between income inequality and the rates of growth and investment with data from broad panel of countries. However, he found two opposite effects of

inequality on growth in poor and rich countries. Inequality retards growth in poor countries in contrast it encourages growth in rich countries. Greater Inequality causes fall in growth when per capita GDP is below around \$ 2000 (1985 US dollar) and inequality causes growth to rise when per capita GDP is over \$ 2000. Growth-inequality relation also depends on the political ideologies of the incumbent government. Socio-democratic ideology leads to inequality-reducing growth policies whereas neoliberal-market ideology lead to growth enhancing policy believing in „trickle down“ effect on poverty alleviation and inequality. Bjørnskov(2008) studied growth-inequality relationship under different government ideologies. The author found negative relationship between inequality and growth under leftwing government and positive relationship under rightwing government.

Although some growth-inequality literature finds positive and zero association between inequality and growth, others argue negative relationship between these two. Reduction in inequality is necessary condition for sustain economic growth. With greater inequality governments are always pressurized for redistribution. Hence, governments have to intervene in the market through tax and subsidy. Pro-poor growth policy may retard the growth in potential sectors. According to neoliberal market philosophy, the less government intervention is in the market the more is economic growth. Thus, reduction in equality smoothens the way of economic growth.

4. Conditionality

There are two propositions that growth is necessary condition for poverty reduction and reduction in inequality is precondition for sustained growth. But these propositions depend on some factors. The first proposition of growth-poverty depends on the nature of poverty. Poverty can be reduced by two broad ways--sustained economic growth and redistribution. If the rate of both absolute and relative poverty is extremely high in an economy due to low wage and unemployment, sustained economic growth may be an immense necessary for poverty reduction. Arguably, economic growth generates employment opportunities at the same time increased wage lifts the poor people out of poverty. In that case, growth-poverty proposition holds. But, if poverty arises due to lack of social security, disability to take part in the market, health and other noneconomic shocks, a distortion-free redistribution from rich to poor may be able to reduce poverty. In that case, growth may not be necessary condition for poverty reduction. Even in a country with zero absolute poverty there may exist high relative poverty. Sustained economic growth may not reduce relative poverty if economic growth pushes up the income of all quintiles of population by the same rate of the economic growth or income of the top quintile increases by more than the rate of economic growth. Then, gap between rich and poor will increase or, at least, will remain same. Nothing will happen to reduction of relative poverty. So, growth policy should be formulated in a way that the income of the poor will increase more than the income of the rich. Or the growth enhances more redistribution of income and wealth from the rich to the poor.

Focusing on inequality-growth arguments, there are two opposing propositions of inequality with growth. On the one hand, savings hypothesis finds positive association between inequality and growth--inequality increases investment thereby enhancing economic growth. On the other hand, socio-political unrest, redistribution-distortion and human capital investment hypotheses tell us that reduction in inequality is a precondition for sustained economic growth. But these propositions

depend on many other factors. Savings hypothesis depends on whether a country is closed or not, capital is mobile or not. In case of a closed economy investment entirely depends on national savings. National savings is also a dominant factor in a country with partially open to international trade and with a partially open capital account. With this situation, reduction in inequality retards the growth process. Otherwise, external capital inflows, FDI bridge the gap between saving and investment. Therefore, in case of free capital mobility, more open to international trade the positive relation of inequality and growth may not hold (Barro 2000). On the contrary, human capital hypothesis finds negative relation between inequality and growth. As poor people make less investment in human capital and other physical capital a redistribution of assets and income from rich to poor enhances the quality and average productivity of investment thereby, stimulating growth process. Again this proposition depends on some factors. Capital market functioning, whether perfect or imperfect, and large set up cost of investment in relation to median income of the country determine the proposition holds or not. If capital market is imperfect poor has limited access to capital market to invest in human capital or physical capital and set up cost of investment is relatively low, the proposition holds. In that case investment opportunities depend entirely on individual income and assets and a low level of investment is able to generate returns because of low level of set up cost (ibid).

Obviously, redistribution benefits the poor and spurs the growth process. However, if capital market is perfect, poor people will not forgo investment in physical capital--it doesn't matter whether redistribution takes place or not. Similarly, if investment generates returns only after a large threshold of investment, redistribution will not help poor people to increase investment both in human capital and physical capital (ibid).

5. A Case Study of Bangladesh

Bangladesh has been chosen for the country case study. In this section this essay attempts to analyse growth, poverty and inequality data of Bangladesh and try to explore the aforesaid propositions. Finally, some light will be shed on overall poverty reduction strategy in Bangladesh. Bangladesh has been experiencing steady growth and reduction in poverty over the time. Figure 3 illustrates growth, poverty and inequality in Bangladesh. From the middle of the 80s percentage of people living under the poverty line, both in terms of Bangladesh national level poverty line and world bank \$1.25/day poverty line, has been falling gradually. In 1984 the poverty head count ratio in terms of world bank measurement (\$1.25/day) was 70 whereas, in 2010, the ratio fell to 43. In terms of national poverty line measurement the ratio was 57 in 1992 and it fell to 32 in 2010.

Figure 3. Poverty Measure, Gini Index and GDP Growth Rate

According to national poverty line, presently one thirds of the total population live under the poverty line. However, inequality first rises then plateaued. In 1984 the Gini index was 26 then it started to rise and is plateaued during the period of 1996 to 2010 with around 33. During the period of 1984 to present the growth rate of GDP showed a little upward trend. In 1984 the growth rate was 5.18 percent and in 2013 it was around 6.5 percent. Although in 80s GDP growth was steady and much higher than that of the previous decades and population growth also was falling, the rate of poverty reduction was not so fast because at that time inequality in income distribution was increasing (Khan and Sen 2001). Poverty reduction during the period of 1996 and 2010 may be credited to the non-increasing-inequality growth. In this period population growth rate decreases as well. During this period absolute poverty goes down because of growth effect and relative poverty

Figure 4. No. of poor people in Bangladesh

Source: World Development Indicator, 2014

remains all the same. However, there is variation in income inequality in rural and urban Bangladesh.

Sometimes it is found that, albeit, poverty is reduced in percentage terms but total number of poor people increase because of high population growth. Figure 4 shows that number of population living under poverty line (\$1.25/day). Line plot of the number of poor people is observed as an inverse U shaped curve. It increases until middle of the 90s then started to fall. This rise may be attributed to the high rate of population growth. During that time population growth was on an average 2.5 percent. After 1995 the population growth rate falls gradually. Accordingly, it is evident that inequality equalizing pro-poor growth has profound effects on poverty alleviation in Bangladesh. Here I would like to discuss the poverty and inequality scenario of Bangladesh from nationally representative micro data.

Unlike, the World Bank measures of US dollar-per-day, Cost of Basic Needs (CBN) method is applied in Bangladesh to measure poverty. Under this measurement the rate of income poverty (Head Count Index) declined from 48.9 to 40.8 percent during the period of 2000 to 2005 (Table 2)*.

Table 2. Trend of Income Poverty

	2010	2005	Annual Change(%) (2005-2010)	2000	Annual Change(%) (2000-2005)
Head Count Index					
National	31.5	40.0	-4.67	48.9	-3.9
Urban	21.3	28.4	-4.28	35.2	-4.2
Rural	35.2	43.8	-5.59	52.3	-3.5
Poverty Gap					
National	6.5	9.0	-6.30	12.8	-6.80
Urban	4.3	6.5	-7.93	9.1	-6.51
Rural	7.4	9.8	-5.46	13.7	-6.48
Squared Poverty Gap					
National	2.0	2.9	-7.16	4.6	-8.81
Urban	1.3	2.1	-9.15	3.3	-8.81
Rural	2.2	3.1	-6.63	4.9	-8.75

Source: Bangladesh Economic Review, 2012

Annual rate of poverty reduction is recorded at 3.9 percent. However, the reduction rate is higher in urban Bangladesh (4.2 %) compared to rural Bangladesh (3.5%). In contrast, during the period from 2005 to 2010 rate of income poverty declined from 40 percent to 31.5 percent. During this period annual rate of poverty reduction was 4.67 percent. But, this time rural poverty is reduced by higher rate (5.59%) compared to the rate in urban area (4.28%).

* All measures of poverty in this table are calculated based on national survey called Household Income and Expenditure Survey (HIES). HIES is conducted by Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics every five years.

Table 3[†] presents data of income distribution in Bangladesh between the period of 2005 to 2010. During this period income share accruing to the lower 5% of household remained same. While, the income share accruing to the top 5% of households increased by 1.5 percentage in 2010. Income distribution among other deciles remains more or less same. Gini coefficient in 2010 declined by about 1 percentage point only.

Table 3: Percentage Distribution of Income Accruing to Households in Groups (Deciles) at National Level and Gini Co-efficient

Household Income Group	2010			2005		
	Total	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban
National	100	100	100	100	100	100
Lower 5%	0.78	0.88	0.78	0.77	0.88	0.67
Decile-1	2.00	2.23	1.98	2.00	2.25	1.80
Decile-2	3.22	3.53	3.09	3.26	3.63	3.02
Decile-9	15.94	15.54	16.08	15.07	15.43	14.48
Decile-10	35.84	33.89	34.77	37.64	33.92	41.08
Top 5%	24.61	22.93	23.39	26.93	23.03	30.37
Gini Co-efficient	0.458	0.430	0.452	0.467	0.428	0.497

Source: Bangladesh Economic Review, 2012

Of course, steady growth in GDP generated employment opportunities in Bangladesh for the unemployed poor. Especially, in manufacturing and service sectors employment generation is higher. Each and every year huge amount of labour enter the job market as Bangladesh is one of the mostly populated countries in the world. Poverty reduction has become a great challenge as population increases greater in number each year. Because of the steady GDP growth the economy of Bangladesh is generating extra employment opportunities for the increasing population. However, not only GDP growth but also many other targeted policies and interventions are responsible for the falling trend of poverty in Bangladesh.

According to World Bank (2014) statistics 67 percent of total population live in rural area in Bangladesh. In rural Bangladesh main source of earnings are agriculture, livestock and fishery. Second largest source is wage income. Although the share of agriculture to GDP is falling over time, still agriculture employs largest share of labour force (47%). Subsidy to agriculture has direct impact on poverty alleviation. Subsidies to agricultural inputs, supply of low interest bearing agricultural credit guard the poor people against uncertainty and volatility of their income. Commercialization of agriculture is also a commendable change in rural Bangladesh that paves the way of poverty alleviation.

In and out migration also plays important role in poverty alleviation in Bangladesh (see Afsar 2003, Hatemi-J and Uddin 2014). As labour market in rural area has already been saturated, people are migrating to urban areas and to overseas countries. Steadily growing Ready Made Garments (RMG) sector in Bangladesh absorbs the surplus poor labour, especially the women. According to

[†]Distribution of income and Gini Coefficients are calculated based on Household Income and Expenditure Survey (HIES).

Bangladesh Bureau of Manpower, Employment and Training(2015), at present around 9 million Bangladeshis are working abroad. In 2013, international personal remittance inflows were amounting to about \$ 13,857 million which is 9.24 % of GDP. These international and national remittance inflows to rural area are reducing income poverty as well as stimulating informal entrepreneurial sector. In addition, supply of small credit helps flourish informal entrepreneurial sector.

Despite the criticism of micro-credit program for its high rate of interest, this program is believed to be a catalyst for poverty reduction in Bangladesh. Micro-credit programs has stimulated informal entrepreneurial sector both in urban and rural areas. It has transformed rural society through empowerment of women, raising social awareness, removing anti-economic socio-religious impediments. Because of this transformation, women have become more entrepreneurial and economically active.

More public expenditure on primary and secondary education has both poverty and inequality reducing effects. Recently, Bangladesh government gives priority on education in budgetary allocation. In Bangladesh,albeit, personal income tax rate is progressive tax revenue in this head is low compared to other indirect taxes such as Value Added Tax (VAT), import tariffs and sales tax. But these indirect taxes are more distortionary which causes escalation of inflation and thereby affectingthe hard core poor inversely.

Along with pro-poor growth polices Bangladesh government runs a number of poverty reducing social safety net programs. These programs are divided into four categories such as cash transfer program, food assistance program, direct employment generation for the poor and micro-credit program. Under cash transfer program there are some sub programs such as old-age allowance, allowance for physically challenged insolvent citizen, allownace for widowed, deserted and destitute women. Food assistance programs are aimed to help the poor in tackling inflation in food items and attaining nutritional fulfillment. Major food assistance programs are food for works, vulnerable group development (VGD),and vulnerable group feeding (VGF). Along with private micro-credit organization, government directly runs some micro-credit programs aimingpoverty alleviation through employment generation. Rate of interest in government run micro-credit program is very lowcompared to the private ones. Besides, there are some micro-credit programs by government commercial and specialized banks. There are also poverty-targeting fund and activities under different ministries. Nobel laureate NGO, Grameen Bank ,and another world renowned large NGO, BRAC, are originated in Bangladesh and are in operation in Bangladesh. These two large NGOs play important role in poverty reduction as well. Hence, the synergy of pro-poor growth policy, poverty targeting programs,redistribution, rural transformation, in and out migration, NGO activities, poverty reducing foreign aid helps reduce poverty in Bangladesh.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, there is a negative relation between economic growth and poverty. Studies find that with economic growth, average income of the poor increases by more than the rate of growth or at least by the same rate. However, not only growth can reduce poverty but also reduction in inequality is required. Global inequality remains stagnant for decades. In some parts of the world, especially in Latin America, problem of inequality is severe (Williamson 2009, Milanovic 2013).

Reduction in inequality is also a precondition for sustained economic growth. With the presence of inequality governments are pressurized to intervene market which distorts efficient allocation of productive resources. Or extreme inequality may lead to socio-political unrest which deters economic growth. However, sustained growth may lead to further inequality (see UNDP 2013). These growth-poverty-inequality propositions depend on many more conditions as well. It depends on the nature of the economy, its capital market, size of population, tax system and rate and depth of poverty, inequality themselves. Since there is a dilemma in growth and equality--achieving one goal may pull apart another goal--policy planners should put more emphasis on equalizing growth policy and implementations. For example, expanded education and more equitable land distribution may narrow down inequality and at the same time also stimulate economic growth (Land and Squire 2003)

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